

Academic editor: Imre Fazekas

Received: 02.05.2023 | Accepted: 25.05.2023 | Published: 28.06.2023. (online)

Light-Trap Catch of Some Beetle (Coleoptera) Species from Tasmania, Hungary and Nebraska Influenced by the Geomagnetic Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

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Abstract. The present study deals with the connection of geomagnetic (Disturbance Storm Time D_{st}) and light-trap catches of some beetle species from Hungary, Tasmania, and Nebraska. Most of the examined species on all three continents were members of the Scarabaeidae family. The light source used was krypton in Hungary, mercury vapor light in Tasmania and black light in Nebraska. For each species, a relationship was found between the values of geo-magnetic Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st}) and the number of beetles captured. However, the results were not identical. Four types were identified: increasing catching type, decreasing catching type, increasing then decreasing catching type and decreasing then increasing catching type.

Keywords. Disturbance Storm Time, light-traps, beetles

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Összefoglalás. Jelen tanulmány a földmágneses zavarokat kifejező D_{st} -index összefüggését vizsgálja az egyes Magyarországon, Tasmanián és Nebraskán területén fénycsapdázott bogárfajok mennyiségével. A vizsgált fajok többsége mindhárom kontinensen a Scarabaeidae család tagja volt. A használt fényforrás Magyarországon kripton, Tasmaniában higanylámpa, Nebraskában UV fény volt. Minden faj esetében összefüggést találtunk a D_{st} értékei és a befogott bogarak száma között. Az eredmények azonban nem voltak azonosak. Négy típust azonosítottunk: növekvő fogási típust, csökkenő fogást, növekvő majd csökkenő fogást és csökkenő majd növekvő fogást. Kulcsszavak: D_{st} index, fénycsapdák, bogarak

Introduction

Researchers worldwide collect many beetle (Coleoptera) species with light-traps for various purposes. Edwards (1961) and Hosking (1979) found the light-trap took 11 families, 27 species, and 752 individuals in New Zealand.

Using a 15W fluorescent UV light-trap in South Carolina, USA (Day & Reid 1969) analysed the catch results of the Southern Potato Wireworm *Conoderus falli* Lane, (Coleoptera: Elateridae) in periods when the Moon was not above the horizon. Matalin deals with Carabidae in several studies (1994, 1996, 1997, 1998). We cannot comment on these works in detail in this study, but some foreign and Hungarian research papers are quoted.

Tóth (1975) found that *Serica brunnea* L. is the prevalent species everywhere in the Carpathian Basin, but the damage made by it is significant only in some regions.

Homonnay (1977) and Járfás & Tóth (1977) dealt with the light trapping of the *Melolontha* species. Bürgés (1982) discussed the influencing factors of light trapping of the Chestnut Beetle (*Curculio elephas* Gyll.) and its forecasting.

The relationship between geomagnetic indices and light trapping of insects was mostly

studied by Finnish, Russian and then Hungarian researchers. Iso-Ivari and Koponen (1976) studied the effect of geomagnetism on the collection of insects in light-traps in the northernmost part of Finland. In their experiments, they used the K index values measured every three hours as well as the ΣK and δH values. A weak but significant correlation was found between geomagnetic parameters and specimens of different orders of captured insects.

Tshernyshev (1965, 1966) reported that the number of light-trapped insects significantly rose at the time of magnetic perturbations. Later, however, he reported that while light-trap catches of some Coleoptera and Lepidoptera species increased, that of other Lepidoptera and Diptera species fell back during magnetic perturbations (Tshernyshev 1972).

Studies by Baker & Mather (1982) and Baker (1987) have also confirmed that some Lepidoptera species, such as Large Yellow Underwing (*Noctua pronuba* L.) and Heart & Dart (*Agrotis exclamationis* L.) are guided by both the Moon and geomagnetism in their orientation, and they are even capable of integrating these two sources of information. On cloudy nights, the imagoes of Large Yellow Underwing (*Noctua pronuba* L.) orientated with the help of geomagnetism.

We have already found that the H-index influences the efficiency of light trapping (Nowinszky & Puskás, 2015). We found a connection between the catch of a composite taxon of several indeterminate Microlepidopteran species and Kp and M-indices (Nowinszky et al. 2016a). We examined the effect of Kp and M-indices on changes in the number of Macrolepidopteran individuals and species (Nowinszky & Puskás 2016b). In a previous study we studied light trapping of caddisfly (Trichoptera) species in connection with the geomagnetic H-index. Different results were obtained for different species. Positive and negative relationships were both found on the rising values of the H index (Nowinszky et al. 2016). The study of Puskás et al. (2018) deals with the light-trap catch of a composite taxon of several indeterminate Microlepidoptera species in connection with the geomagnetic M-index. They found the catch of Microlepidoptera species decreased at high M-index values.

Recently, we also found a relationship between the D_{st} index and the effectiveness of light-trap catching of eight caddisfly (Trichoptera) species (Nowinszky et al. 2021).

Material

The D_{st} (Disturbance Storm Time) index has been used since 1957/58. It characterizes the earthly manifestations of space weather by measuring the strength of the ring current around the Earth, which is created by protons and electrons originating from the Sun.

Large disturbances of the Earth's magnetic field, the so-called geomagnetic storms, are defined by changes in the D_{st} (Disturbance Storm Time) index. The D_{st} index determines the globally averaged change of the horizontal component of the Earth's magnetic field at the magnetic equator. It is computed once per hour based on measurements from a few stations at low latitudes (Honolulu, San Juan, Hermanus, and Kakioka). The size of a geomagnetic storm is classified as moderate ($-50 \text{ nT} > \text{minimum of } D_{st} > -100 \text{ nT}$), intense ($-100 \text{ nT} > \text{minimum } D_{st} > -250 \text{ nT}$) or super-storm minimum of $D_{st} (< -250 \text{ nT})$. During quiet times D_{st} is between +20 and -20 nanoTesla (nT).

The data of hourly equatorial D_{st} values (Final) that we use was published by WDC Kyoto Observatory.

The light-trap data of examined species except the *Curculio elephas* (Gyllenhaal) were taken from the data base of the Hungarian Forestry Light-trap Network of the Forest Research Institute, which operated 8 light-trap stations across the whole territory of Hungary for many years. The catching data of *Curculio elephas* (Gyll.) are the trapping results of Bürgés. His Jermy-type light-traps were in operation in 1973, 1974 and 1977 around Rezi and in 1979 at Zengővárkony. We processed the catch data of the *Curculio elephas* (Gyll.) from this material which was 2230 individuals during the 105 nights.

The light-trap stations, geographic coordinates and years of operation are presented in Table 2. 1.

The Tasmanian data derive from decades of near-continuous (1992–2019) operation of a

Table 1. Light-trap stations, geographic coordinates and years

Light-trap stations	Geographical coordinates	Years
Budakeszi	47°30'83"N — 18°56'03"E	1961—1975
Farkasgyepű	47°12'22"N — 17°38'02"E	1965—1990
Gyulaj	46°30'51"N — 18°17'76"E	1969—1980
Kunfehértó	46°21'64"N — 19°24'93"E	1961—1975
Makkoshotyka	48°21'52"N — 21°31'17"E	1961—1988
Mátraháza	47°46'87"N — 19°55'69"E	1961—1992
Várgesztes	47°28'52"N — 18°23'91"E	1962—1992
Rezi	46°50'54"N — 17°13'26"E	1973, 1974, 1977
Zengővárkony	46°10'38"N — 18°25'96"E	1979

160W mercury vapour light-trap at Stony Rise in Tasmania, Australia. A history of the Tasmanian program was published by Hill (2013). This includes a list of many of the species enumerated at the Stony Rise trap. The trap was like the Rothamsted-design traps operated in the United Kingdom for decades. It was located at the edge of the small city of Devonport, which is central on the north coast of Tasmania. The trap was at 41°11'29" S, 146°19'24" E (41.18°S 146.32°E), at a site 69 m above sea level and 5 km south of Bass Strait, which separates the island state of Tasmania from mainland Australia.

The following institutes operate light-traps at 4 locations in the state of Nebraska:
 Nebraska Research, Extension, and Education Center, Mead
 Haskell Agricultural Laboratory
 University of Nebraska, South Central Agricultural Laboratory
 Agroecosystems Entomology Laboratory, North Platte

Methods

Basic data were the number of beetles caught in one night. To compare the differing sampling data, relative values were calculated from the number of beetles for each sampling night per each year. The relative catch value (RC) was defined as the quotient of the number of beetles caught during a sampling time unit (1 night) per the average nightly catch of beetles within the relevant sampling period (Nowinszky 2003). In this work, the sampling period means all the nights of all the years in which the catch of certain species was successful.

Separately, all catch data by species were considered as a single sample and thus relative

Table 2. The name of families, species, years, number of individuals and nights

Families and Species	Years	Number of		
		Traps	Moths	Data
HUNGARY				
Tenebrionidae				
<i>Hymenalia rufipes</i> Fabricius, 1792	1969-1974	3	3585	385
Darking Beetle <i>Lagria hirta</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1963-1970	8	815	346
Scarabaeidae				
Brown Chafer <i>Serica brunnea</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1969-1974	6	7,700	499
April Beetle <i>Holocheilus aequinoctialis</i> Herbst, 1790	2004-2011	2	1,924	272
Brown Coloured Beetle <i>Rhizotrogus aestivus</i> Olivier, 1789	1967-1974	2	1,953	160
Summer Chafer <i>Amphimallon solstitialis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1987-2000	4	1,282	340
Common Chockchafer <i>Melolontha melolontha</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1966-2010	45	48,295	8399
Curculionidae				
Chestnut Beetle <i>Curculio elephas</i> Gyllenhal, 1836	1973-1974, 1977, 1979	3	3,093	150
TASMANIA (STONY RICE)				
Scarabaeidae				
Black-Headed Cockchafer <i>Acrossidius tasmaniae</i> Hope, 1846	1992-2006 2010-219	1	15,401	560
Nectar Scarab <i>Phyllotocus bimaculatus</i> Erichson, 1842	2015-2019	1	2,222	185
<i>Heteronyx</i> sp.	2016-2019	1	1,665	180
NEBRASKA				
Scarabaeidae				
Masked Chafer <i>Cyclocephala borealis</i> Arrow, 1911	1998-2005	1	71,696	374
Scarab Beetles <i>Phyllophaga</i> sp.	2009-2017	4	50,431	775

catch values were calculated. This solution also made it possible to determine the effectiveness of trapping from the relative catch values of each year and to compare the effectiveness of the years. For example, when the actual nightly catch was equal to the average nightly catch in the relevant summer, the RC was 1 (Nowinszky 2003).

Paired data of catch and Dst values were grouped into classes based on Dst values. The number of these classes was calculated with consideration to the method of Sturges (Odor & Iglói 1987) by use of the following formula:

$$k = 1 + 3.3 * 1g n$$

Where: k = the number of classes, n = the number of observation data.

Within a class, however, it is not reasonable to have big differences in the amount of data. Therefore, the classes at the two extremities are wider than those in the middle. Within each group we used our own method and calculated three point weighted moving averages from the values of the catching data. Earlier, there was a problem about moving averaging, namely, that the first and last values, the ones carrying in many cases valuable information on the most important biological impacts were lost. In elaborating our method, we also considered the work of (Urmancev 1967). He came up with a solution to ensure that no data is lost, with every initial data being accompanied by a moving average value. The new method also considers with differing weights the middle, previous and following values. Thanks to this method, our moving averages get weighted with the number of initial data. The 3-point moving average is calculated based on the following formula:

$$\text{The first value: } \frac{7\Sigma x_1 + 4\Sigma x_2 - 2x_3}{7n_1 + 4n_2 - 2n_3}$$

$$\text{The last value: } \frac{7\Sigma x_h + 4\Sigma x_{h-1} - 2\Sigma x_{h-2}}{7n_h + 4n_{h-1} - 2n_{h-2}}$$

$$\text{The remaining values: } \frac{\Sigma x_{i-1} + 2\Sigma x_i + \Sigma x_{i+1}}{n_{i-1} + 2n_i + n_{i+1}}$$

The use of moving averages is justified whenever the independent variable is made up of data representing a wide range of values that are to be contracted into classes. The dividing line between these classes is always drawn arbitrarily. Besides, extreme values in two neighbouring classes of the environmental factor are always closer to each other than they are to the middle value of their own class. Working with moving averages ensures a degree of continuity between the data of our arbitrarily established classes and, at least in part, eliminates the disturbing influence of another environmental factor not examined in the given context (Nowinszky 2003). Finally, we averaged within groups the D_{st} index and relative catch data pairs. We made figures from the results.

Results and Discussion

Our results are shown in Figures 1—13.

These results prove that beetles can be classified into four behaviour types:

Catch increasing with increasing Dst: *Hymenalia rufipes* (Fabricius, 1792), *Holochelus aequinoctialis* (Herbst, 1790), *Melolontha melolontha* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Cyclocephala borealis* (Arrow, 1911), *Phyllophaga* sp.

Decreasing: *Rhizotrogus aestivus* (Olivier, 1789), *Amphimalon solstitialis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Acrossidius tasmaniae* (Hope, 1846).

Increasing then decreasing: *Serica brunnea* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Decreasing then increasing: *Lagria hirta* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Curculio elephas* (Gyllenhal, 1836), *Phyllotocus bimaculatus* (Erichson, 1842), *Heteronyx* sp.

According to our hypothesis, the explanation of our results can be the following: The increase or decrease of the catch is explainable by our previous hypotheses (Nowinszky 2003). The variable flight response has many reasons. Species differ in their tolerance of environmental factors. These factors interact with each other to exert their effects. Thus, the same factor can result in different effects at various times. The individuals of any species have different survival strategies. Adverse effects have two possible answers: passivity, or hiding or even increased activity, because this behaviour ensures the survival of the species. That is, the insects attempt "to carry out their duties in a hurry".

The low relative catch values always refer to situations in which the flight activity of insects diminishes. However, high values are not so simply interpreted. In our hypothesis, the individual may adopt two kinds of strategies to evade the impacts hindering the normal functioning of its life phenomena. It may either display more liveliness, by increasing the intensity of its flight, copulation and egg-laying activity or take refuge in passivity to weather, an unfavourable situation. And so, by the present state of our knowledge, we might say that favourable and unfavourable environmental effects might equally be accompanied by a high catch (Nowinszky 2003).

The explanation for the increasing type is that even moderate values of geomagnetic storm D_{st} becomes increasingly more negative are unfavourable for these species.

The explanation of the increasing and then decreasing type, according to our hypothesis, may be as follows. Initially, some environmental factor enhances insect activity. However, a stronger effect subsequently forces it into passivity.

The decreasing and then increasing type is harder to explain. We must assume that even moths belonging to the same species do not behave identically. According to our hypothesis, the activity of a part of the population increases during geomagnetic storm moderate values, while other individuals of the population increase during quiet time. It can be assumed that this mode of behaviour ensures the survival of the population even in highly unfavourable situations. This phenomenon may be like the sensitivity to hot and cold fronts observed in humans. However, it is striking that these types of responses by species are independent of the continent.

Acknowledgements. We thank Imre Fazekas, editor, for the pictures of the species and the maps (text-figure 1. and Figure 14.).

Text-figure 1. For the geographical location of the sites in Hungary (see Table 1). Graphic: by Imre Fazekas

Figure 1 Light-trap catch of *Hymenalia rufipes* Fabricius, 1792 in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 2 Light-trap catch of Darkling Beetle (*Lagria hirta* Linnaeus, 1758) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Lagria hirta, adult >

Figure 3 Light-trap catch of Brown Chafer (*Serica brunnea* Linnaeus, 1758) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 4 Light-trap catch of April Beetle (*Holocheilus aequinoctialis* Herbst, 1790) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Holocheilus aequinoctialis >

Figure 5 Light-trap catch of Brown Coloured Beetle (*Rhizotrogus aestivus* Olivier, 1789) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 6 Light-trap catch of Summer Chafer (*Amphimalon solstitialis* Linnaeus, 1758) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Amphimalon solstitialis >

Figure 7 Light-trap catch of Cockchafer Beetle (*Melolontha melolontha* Linnaeus, 1758) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 8 Light-trap catch of Chestnut Weevil (*Curculio elephas* Gyllenhal, 1836) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Curculio elephas >

Figure 9. Light-trap catch of Black-Headed Cockchafer (*Acrossidius tasmaniae* Hope, 1846) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 10. Light-trap catch of Nectar Scarab (*Phyllotocus bimaculatus* Erichson, 1842) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Phyllotocus bimaculatus >

Figure 11. Light-trap catch of *Heteronyx* sp. in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 12. Light-trap catch of Masked Chafer (*Cyclocephala borealis* Arrow, 1911) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Cyclocephala borealis >

Figure 13. Light-trap catch of Scarab Beetles (*Phyllophaga* sp.) in connection with the Disturbance Storm Time (D_{st})

Figure 14. Geographical location of research sites on the world map (© Fazekas Imre)

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